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Generative AI and Academic Scientists in US universities: Perception,
Experience, and Adoption Intentions

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26 **Abstract**

27 The integration of generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) into academia has sparked
28 interest and debate among academic scientists. This paper explores the early adoption and
29 perceptions of US academic scientists regarding the use of generative AI in teaching and
30 research activities. To do so, this analysis focuses exclusively on STEM fields due to their high
31 exposure to rapid technological advancements. Drawing from a nationally representative survey
32 of 232 respondents, we examine academic scientists' attitudes, experiences, and intentions
33 regarding AI adoption. Results indicate that 65% of respondents have utilized generative AI in
34 teaching or research activities, with 20% applying it in both areas. Among those currently using
35 AI, 84% intend to continue its application, indicating a high level of confidence in its perceived
36 benefits. AI is most frequently used in teaching to develop pedagogical materials (51%) and in
37 research for writing, reviewing, and editing tasks (40%). Despite concerns about
38 misinformation, with 78% of respondents indicating it as their top concern regarding AI, there
39 is broad recognition of AI' s potential impact on society. Most academic scientists have
40 already integrated AI into their academic activities, demonstrating cautious yet optimistic
41 adoption due to perceived risks. Furthermore, there is strong support for academic-led
42 regulation of AI, highlighting the need for responsible governance to maximize benefits while
43 minimizing risks in educational and research settings.

44

45 **Introduction**

46 Research in Artificial Intelligence (AI) has a storied past, beginning when the term was
47 first coined at the 1956 Dartmouth Summer Research Project on Artificial Intelligence [1]. Fast
48 forward to late 2022, the release of ChatGPT (<https://openai.com/blog/chatgpt>) marked a
49 significant milestone in AI, democratizing access to advanced generative AI technologies.

50 Generative AI refers to a subset of artificial intelligence that is designed to create new content,
51 such as text, images, audio, video, and even code, based on patterns learned from large datasets
52 [2]. Unlike traditional AI systems, which function based on pre-defined rules, generative AI
53 systems demonstrate greater functional autonomy and ability to perform intelligent behaviors
54 in a way that mimic human creativity by learning patterns and behaviors from data [3]. The rise
55 of generative AI, particularly through chatbots powered by including Large Language Models
56 (LLM), further exemplifies the impact of these technologies on various domains. The rapid
57 development of chatbots beyond ChatGPT has sparked considerable interest [4]. The
58 widespread adoption of these AI tools has the potential to alter numerous elements of society,
59 including impacting higher education and scientific research [5,6]. The ability of generative AI
60 to produce text that is virtually indistinguishable from human-written work promises to
61 transform educational methodologies and research practices, offering new opportunities for
62 institutions, educators, and students [7,8]. This rapid expansion has also raised important
63 questions regarding risks such as bias, transparency, and social impact [9].

64

65 The significance of generative AI's impact is particularly evident in Science, Technology,
66 Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) fields. The importance of these fields is underscored
67 by the growing number of students pursuing STEM disciplines, a trend influenced by various
68 factors and reflective of a country's economic development [10]. Simultaneously, since 2015,
69 US companies have been increasing their demand for AI-related expertise and are recruiting
70 early-career AI researchers from academia [11,12]. This growth and demand highlight the
71 importance of integrating AI into educational curricula and research methodologies to keep
72 pace with technological advancements and opportunities. Understanding their perspectives on
73 and experiences with AI is essential, as these academic scientists can provide valuable technical
74 input for its ongoing development across various disciplines [13].

75

76 Given the rapid global adoption of generative AI, this article explores the early adoption
77 behaviors and perceptions of US academic scientists related to teaching and research activities.
78 According to innovation diffusion theory [14], early adopters are different from late adopters
79 as they often face higher uncertainty and different motivations compared to later adopters. In
80 this context, early adoption refers to the initial phase of AI integration before it becomes
81 widespread in academia. While the study is centered on the United States, the insights can be
82 considered reflective of broader international trends due to the influential role of US academia
83 on a global scale [15]. To achieve these insights, we draw from a nationally representative
84 survey of academic scientists, that include assistant, associate and full professors, across six
85 disciplines—biology, chemistry, computer and information science engineering, civil and
86 environmental engineering, geography, and public health—at randomly selected Carnegie-
87 designated Research Extensive and Intensive (R1) universities. The study is designed as a
88 descriptive and exploratory analysis of academic scientists’ reported attitudes, experiences, and
89 uses of generative AI. The following aims were established to effectively address this main
90 objective:

- 91 1. To assess the general attitudes of academic scientists towards generative AI.
- 92 2. To explore the perceptions and experiences of academic scientists regarding the use of
93 AI in academic teaching and research.
- 94 3. To examine how academic scientists’ adoption intention for teaching and research
95 varies.
- 96 4. To investigate academic scientists concerns and perceptions regarding the regulation of
97 generative AI.

98

99 The next section presents a literature on the use of AI in higher education. It explores how
100 academic scientists from different disciplines perceive its application and reviews other survey-
101 based research on this topic. The subsequent methodology section describes the methods and
102 data collection process is followed by a results section that presents the findings of the survey,
103 detailing academic scientists' perceptions, experiences, and intentions regarding generative AI
104 in teaching and research. The conclusion section synthesizes key insights and points out
105 limitations of the study.

106

107 **Literature review**

108 The following review is structured around the benefits and risks of generative AI in
109 academia, setting the stage for an exploratory analysis of scientists' behaviors and perceptions.

110

111 **Generative AI in Academic Education**

112 Artificial intelligence (AI) has long been an integral part of higher education at different
113 levels, significantly predating the recent explosion in AI technologies such as ChatGPT,
114 Microsoft Copilot or Elicit [16]. In its early applications in this context, AI was employed to
115 streamline complex administrative tasks, enhancing efficiency in areas like admissions
116 processes and predicting student retention rates, which are crucial for institutional planning
117 [17,18]. Additionally, academic libraries began to leverage AI for automated cataloging,
118 intelligent search tools, AI-driven reference services, and adaptive learning systems, improving
119 accessibility and operational efficiency [19].

120 More recently, generative AI tools has introduced new possibilities and challenges across
121 various domains in higher education [20]. AI is used to personalize learning through adaptive
122 tutoring systems and identify and address student learning obstacles [21,22]. Advocates suggest

123 that generative AI-enhanced personalized education could improve learning outcomes, increase
124 accessibility, reduce inequities [23–26], and enhance student interaction and engagement [27–
125 29]. Moreover, AI is increasingly used to assist in assessment processes, making them more
126 accurate and less time-consuming, and enabling automated grading that involves text
127 generation [22, 24,25]. Although these applications have relied on specialized and custom-
128 designed applications that are not universally accessible, they are beginning to transform the
129 higher education system by offering institutions and individuals substantial administrative and
130 educational benefits. Educators recognize that the impact on education will vary by discipline
131 and require changes in teaching methods [33].

132

133 Despite the perceived usefulness and improved ease of communication [34], there is
134 insufficient understanding of generative AI’s long-term impacts on educational practices,
135 particularly regarding sustained changes in teaching methods and learning outcomes [35], and
136 of how academic scientists perceive and respond to these developments. These uncertainties
137 are further complicated by significant, pre-existing concerns regarding the reliability and safety
138 of AI systems in education, issues which have broadened and intensified following generative
139 AI’s widespread adoption [36–38]. Notable issues include the risk of overreliance on AI and its
140 effects on critical thinking [31,39] and AI’s potential to undermine creativity, hinder academic
141 integrity, and reinforce existing inequalities due to biases in datasets, algorithmic opacity, and
142 disparities in access to AI-driven tools [40]. AI’s potential to undermine creativity, hinder
143 academic integrity, and exacerbate existing inequalities is reflected in disparities in access to
144 AI tools and the reinforcement of biases within algorithmic decision-making. Generative AI
145 can also compromise academic standards through plagiarism [26] and generate misleading or
146 fabricated information, thereby undermining trust [41]. Concerns also remain about fairness,
147 responsibility, and the necessity for clear guidelines and training to ensure generative AI’s

148 ethical and effective implementation [42,43]. While AI integration offers benefits like improved
149 accessibility and efficiency, it also raises fears about job obsolescence due to the evolving
150 demand for new skills and competencies [44]. These concerns point to a growing need for
151 human oversight to safeguard academic integrity and mitigate bias [31,45], as the adoption of
152 generative AI in education raises significant challenges related to critical thinking, fairness, and
153 equitable access to learning opportunities.

154

155 **Generative AI in Academic Research**

156 Generative AI is also having a substantial impact on academic research. Messeri and
157 Crockett [46] have outlined a typology of four different roles generative AI can play in research:
158 oracle for study design, surrogate for data collection, quant for data analysis, and arbiter for
159 peer review. Generative AI tools have sparked interest for their potential in various tasks along
160 the research pipeline of discovery by facilitating the synthesis and understanding of scientific
161 literature, generating and organizing ideas, providing targeted feedback, and analyzing vast
162 amounts of data to uncover connections, thus streamlining research processes and mitigating
163 some types of cognitive biases [47]. Additionally, AI models can improve the prediction of
164 future discoveries, especially in areas with limited literature, by anticipating human predictions
165 and identifying key researchers [48] or by acting as "an autonomous researcher," to produce
166 new knowledge [49].

167

168 While many of the applications of generative AI to research activities appear promising,
169 challenges and risks still loom large [5,50,51]. For example, the expansion of Large Language
170 Models for broader use presents significant threats to research integrity, impacting its
171 transparency, reliability, and authenticity [51–53]. This can be seen in how AI systems can

172 introduce biases from their training data, potentially perpetuating hidden prejudices and
173 undermining the integrity and authenticity of scientific knowledge [54]. As universities start to
174 craft generative AI guidelines [55], academic scientists' excitement about potential efficiency
175 gains is balanced by concerns over risks such as misinformation, plagiarism, and falsified
176 research [50,56]. For example, while generative AI can produce high-quality text suitable for
177 publication, its limited capacity for research design and data analysis increases the risk of
178 misinformation, fabricated findings, and academic integrity violations [57]. Moreover,
179 concerns have been raised about who owns the AI-generated content [58], whether it maintains
180 its integrity [59], and what the risks are to data privacy when sharing protected information
181 [60]. These issues pose serious challenges that could affect the perceptions and behaviors of
182 academic scientists leading to caution in embracing these technologies and potentially slowing
183 down their integration into research practices.

184

185 **Academic Perceptions about and Adoption of Generative AI**

186 Understanding academic scientists' perceptions of generative AI is crucial because of its
187 potential to radically transform research and teaching landscapes in higher education, affecting
188 vast segments of the US and international academic communities. Conceptual frameworks such
189 as the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) [61], the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) [62], the
190 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) [63], the Innovation Diffusion Theory [64] and the
191 Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) [65] provide valuable
192 frameworks for examining technology acceptance. Cumulatively, they highlight the importance
193 of personal beliefs and attitudes, including concerns [66] confidence and readiness [63,67], as
194 well as past experiences [67] in shaping technology acceptance. However, the implications of
195 AI extend beyond adoption frameworks; AI's integration into academic environments presents

196 unprecedented opportunities and significant uncertainties, making it imperative to closely
197 monitor how these changes unfold over time.

198

199 While educators and researchers recognize AI as a valuable tool for developing new ideas,
200 streamlining workflows, and offering remote and personalized learning experiences [68–70],
201 they have also expressed ethical concerns regarding plagiarism, misinformation, and
202 misidentification of AI-produced content as human work. The challenge of accurately detecting
203 AI-generated text is significant, as current classifiers often misclassify human-written text as
204 generated by AI and vice versa [71,72]. These risks affect various fields differently. For
205 instance, in medical education, while there is optimism about AI’s potential to reduce
206 administrative burdens and enhance diagnostic accuracy, concerns persist about data privacy,
207 the potential for AI-generated medical content to be overly relied upon without human
208 oversight, and the challenges of ensuring the accuracy and reliability of AI-assisted educational
209 tools [73]. Researchers in population health and academic publishing have also voiced concerns
210 over sensationalist media portrayals of generative AI, stressing the importance of better
211 education and awareness raising to combat these misconceptions [74,75]. Additionally, AI and
212 machine learning specialists have identified a need for more safety research and exhibit low
213 levels of trust in certain organizations managing AI technologies [76]. Given the complex and
214 uncertain consequences of AI integration into academia, systematic tracking and continuous
215 evaluation of this transformation are essential to responsibly navigate the potential benefits and
216 risks.

217

218 With its significant promise for advancing education and research, generative AI presents
219 both compelling opportunities and serious concerns. Understanding how academic scientists
220 weigh these perceived benefits against potential risks is essential for assessing whether adoption

221 is likely to accelerate, slow down, or proceed cautiously. However, few studies have jointly
222 addressed STEM academic scientists' perceptions of, experiences with, and generative AI
223 adoption intentions in both education and research. In order to bridge this gap, this study
224 develops a comprehensive approach to better delineate the current state and more accurately
225 understand the adoption rationales of academic scientists. We believe such research is a
226 prerequisite for tailoring educational methodologies, enhancing research practices, and
227 addressing concerns regarding the regulation of generative AI.

228

229 **Material and methods**

230 We make use of a unique database consisting of two sets of merged survey data from the
231 SciOPS (Scientist Opinion Panel Survey): an intake survey administered in the Spring of 2022
232 and 2023 to collect general socio-demographic data regarding SciOPS panelists, and another
233 survey of panelists' attitudes towards AI that was administered in late 2023 (hereafter, the AI
234 survey). SciOPS is a platform to improve science communication between university academic
235 scientists and the public by understanding scientist opinions on current topics relevant to the
236 science community and to society. Detailed information regarding SciOPS and past surveys
237 administrated by this platform can be found at SciOPS website [77].

238

239 This study employed a two-stage sampling design. At the first stage, SciOPS panel
240 members were recruited from a full sample frame that includes approximately 18,500 PhD-
241 level academic scientists employed by Carnegie-designated Research Extensive and Intensive
242 (R1) universities across the US, representing six STEM fields: biology, chemistry, civil and
243 environmental engineering, computer and information science engineering, geography, and
244 public health. The SciOPS research team used probability sampling to randomly select R1

245 universities and collected the names and contact information of tenured and tenure track faculty
246 (i.e., assistant, associate, and full professors), and non-tenure track researchers with PhDs from
247 each sampled academic department website. Fields and ranks were collected by the SciOPS
248 research team from their personal profile on their institution websites. Table S3 in S2 Appendix
249 shows the number of randomly selected institutions by field.

250

251 A total of 1,365 eligible academic scientists consented to become SciOPS panel members,
252 with a recruitment rate of 7.5%, calculated according to the guidance of American Association
253 for Public Opinion Research (AAPOR) Recruitment Rate formula [78]. The intake survey was
254 dispensed to all 1,365 members to capture their general socio-demographic information,
255 including birth year, self-reported gender, citizenship, academic rank, and academic discipline.

256

257 In the second stage, 777 SciOPS panel members were randomly selected from all
258 members and invited to participate in this survey. To construct valid survey questions, the
259 SciOPS research team designed them based on literature on technology adoption among
260 academic scientists. The questions underwent multiple rounds of review, revision, and internal
261 pretesting by 10 SciOPS research team members. The full questionnaire is available in S3
262 Appendix.

263

264 The survey was administrated online in English through the Nubis® system, which is an
265 online software platform for administering questionnaires with the aim of protecting the
266 confidentiality of survey respondents. A pre-notification electronic email was delivered on
267 September 27, 2023 to notify the sample of a forthcoming survey invitation. We sent email
268 messages with a formal survey invitation to each sampled individual along with a questionnaire
269 hyperlink on September 29. Three formal reminder messages were sent on October 4, October

270 11, and October 18. A final short appeal message was sent on November 2. We closed the
 271 survey on November 4. This survey obtained a total of 232 usable responses, representing an
 272 individual survey completion rate (COMR) of 29.9% (RR4) and an AAPOR Cumulative
 273 Response Rate (CUMRR) of 2.2%. The CUMRR calculated by multiplying the RECR for the
 274 SciOPS panel (7.5%) with the Completion Rate for this survey (29.9%) and dividing by 100.

275

276 **Table 1. Weighted descriptive statistics of the final sample.**

Construct	Variable	N	%
Self-reported Gender	Female	71	31
	Male	155	66
	Prefer not to report	6	3
Field	Biology	16	7
	Chemistry	31	13
	Computer and Information Science Engineering	28	12
	Civil and Environmental Engineering	63	27
	Geography	90	39
	Public Health	4	2
Rank	Full Professor	76	33
	Associate Professor	49	21
	Assistant Professor	49	21
	Non-tenure Track Researcher	58	25
Self-reported Citizenship	Born a U.S. Citizen	135	58
	Naturalized U.S. Citizen	60	26
	Non-U.S. citizen with a permanent U.S. resident visa (e.g. green card)	26	11
	Non-U.S. citizen with a temporary U.S. resident visa	4	2
	Prefer not to answer	7	3

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278 Both surveys were approved by the Institutional Review Board at Arizona State
279 University (IRB Approval No. STUDY00012476). Data were weighted to account for
280 probabilities of selection and post-stratified by gender, academic field, and rank to represent
281 the population of academic scientists from which the full sample was initially recruited. The
282 margin of sampling error for the AI survey estimates is ± 6.4 percentage points, based on a
283 population of 18,504 and a 95% confidence level. Table 1 reports the weighted demographic
284 characteristics of survey respondents.

285

286 Additionally, to assess how variations in question framing might influence academic
287 scientists' attitudes toward government regulation of generative AI, we embedded an
288 experimental design within the survey. Respondents were randomly assigned to one of four
289 versions of a key question, which varied in terms of the inclusion of a moderate response option
290 and the presence or absence of ethical framing regarding potential risks. This design allowed
291 us to examine how different presentations of the same regulatory dilemma influenced
292 participants' preferences.

293

294 To assess the representativeness of our sample, we also conducted a non-response bias
295 analysis (see S1 Appendix for details). The analysis shows minimal differences between the
296 completed sample and the initial sample frame of academic scientists, and no significant
297 differences between our sample and the panel members invited to participate in the survey.
298 These findings confirm that the dataset provides a reasonable representation of US-based
299 academic scientists.

300

301 **Results**

302 Following, we detail survey results on academic scientists' perceptions of generative AI
303 use and regulation, underscoring their experiences and intentions regarding its implementation
304 in teaching and research.

305

306 **General perceptions and practical use of generative AI in academia**

307 Survey responses indicate that a majority of academic scientists (93%) believe that
308 generative AI will have a significant impact on daily life in the United States (Fig 1). The
309 potential effects of climate change also register as a major point of academic concern, albeit
310 slightly less so (88%) than generative AI (though this difference falls within the margin of
311 error), indicating a sense of urgency regarding environmental shifts. While global conflicts
312 (78%), the proliferation of infectious diseases (77%), and the challenges of resource scarcity
313 (72%) are acknowledged, they are perceived as less immediately impactful compared to
314 technological and political shifts on the horizon. Notably, fusion energy, while revolutionary in
315 concept, is seen by academic scientists as trailing behind in terms of imminent impact.

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324 **Fig 1. Academic scientists’ views on the extent to which different issues can cause changes**
 325 **to the way we live in the U.S.**

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328 Fig 2 presents academic scientists’ specific concerns regarding this technology. Foremost
 329 among these is concern over misinformation, which echoes the national discourse on political
 330 polarization, with 78% of respondents marking it as extremely or very concerning. Concerns
 331 extend to an over-dependence on AI technologies and their potential cybersecurity risks, noted
 332 by 60% and 51% of academic scientists, respectively, as major issues; which is followed by the
 333 fear that generative AI may stifle human creativity, with half of the surveyed academic
 334 scientists expressing apprehension. In contrast, issues such as privacy loss and job
 335 displacement, though acknowledged, elicit less concern, where 44% and 24% of respondents
 336 express extremely or very strong concern respectively.

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342 **Fig 2. Academic scientists' level of concern over potential threats posed by generative AI.**

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345 Despite these concerns, there is a noteworthy trend among academic scientists integrating
 346 generative AI into their core activities: teaching and research. A sizable 65% of academic
 347 scientists have personally used generative AI to some extent. Specifically, 40% of surveyed
 348 academic scientists report using generative AI in teaching and research, demonstrating an early
 349 adoption—defined here as the integration of generative AI into academic activities shortly (one
 350 year) after the release of ChatGPT-3.5 in late 2022. In contrast, 25% utilize generative AI for
 351 alternative functions not directly related to their primary roles, and 35% have not engaged with
 352 AI personally. Diving deeper, 20% of academic scientists report using generative AI in both
 353 teaching and research. This is juxtaposed with 11% who use generative AI exclusively for
 354 research and a smaller 9% who apply it solely to teaching.

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358 **Irregular use of generative AI for teaching with persistent** 359 **continuation for adopters**

360 In terms of its adoption for education, generative AI is experiencing early-stage
361 integration by academic scientists in teaching roles, with usage patterns reflecting cautious
362 exploration rather than full integration (Fig 3). The data shows a majority engage with
363 generative AI tools occasionally, reserving them for specific tasks rather than regular use. This
364 tentative approach suggests an awareness of the potential and limitations of current generative
365 AI technologies in educational settings. For those integrating generative AI into their pedagogy,
366 its most common application lies in the development of teaching materials, with 51% of the
367 generative AI-utilizing academic scientists relying on these tools for this purpose. Generative
368 AI is also employed in crafting student assignments (38%) and conducting interactive
369 classroom activities (37%), though less frequently for direct student interactions such as
370 mentoring (17%) or critical tasks like grading (11%) or examinations (8%). The restrained use
371 in these areas may point to a preference for human oversight where subjective judgment and
372 personalized feedback are valued.

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382 **Fig 3. Frequency and Academic scientists use of generative AI for teaching activities.**

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385 Regarding future intentions to use generative AI in teaching, the distinction between
386 current users and non-users is stark. Almost all academic scientists who have integrated
387 generative AI into their teaching methods, 97%, anticipate continuing its use, underscoring a
388 high level of satisfaction and perceived value. In contrast, among those who have not yet
389 employed generative AI in their teaching practice, skepticism is prevalent. A majority, 80%,
390 express reservations about adopting generative AI: within this group, 45% express no intention
391 to use it, and 35% remain undecided. Only 20% of current non-users express openness to future
392 use; within this group, 85% (i.e., 17% of the total) state they are likely to adopt it, while 15%
393 (i.e., 3% of the total) are certain they will incorporate it into their teaching.

394 **Same perspectives and intentions for generative AI use in research**

395 In the realm of research, the adoption of generative AI exhibits trends similar to its use in
396 educational activities (Fig 4). Nearly half (46%) of the researchers surveyed employ generative
397 AI less than once a month, indicating a tentative exploration, and about a quarter (24%) use it
398 on a weekly basis. Additionally, among academic scientists who only use generative AI in
399 research, 40% report finding value in its applications for writing, reviewing, and editing.
400 Significantly, generative AI's role in data analysis (32%) and especially in research
401 conceptualization (28%) marks a shift, indicating its potential not just in routine tasks but in
402 critical thinking and idea generation phases. Moreover, generative AI's application extends to
403 administrative responsibilities like funding acquisition, demonstrating its utility in streamlining
404 research workflows and relieving administrative burden. Additionally, its application in
405 visualization and other specialized tasks further highlights generative AI's versatility and
406 usefulness in the research process.

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418 **Fig 4. Frequency and Academic scientists use of generative AI for research activities.**

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421 Building on the observed patterns of generative AI use in research, future intentions
422 among academic scientists also further highlight the divide between current users and non-
423 users. Those with experience using generative AI in their research overwhelmingly endorse its
424 continued application, with 84% affirming they will likely or definitely continue integrating
425 generative AI into their work. This strong positive sentiment contrasts sharply with the
426 skepticism seen among those yet to adopt generative AI for research, where 78% express
427 reservations. Within this group, a notable 41% are decided against using generative AI, and
428 37% remain uncertain about its potential benefits. Conversely, only a minority are open to the
429 possibility, with 18% leaning towards probable use and a mere 5% convinced of its definite

430 future use. This dichotomy suggests that firsthand experience with generative AI may influence
431 perceptions of its utility, with a divide emerging between adopters and skeptics regarding its
432 role in research activities.

433

434 **The university as main regulatory agent and concerns about its** 435 **regulation**

436 Following the exploration of academic scientists' perspectives and their usage of
437 generative AI, attention shifts to the question of regulatory oversight. Within this domain, there
438 emerges a clear consensus favoring academic institutions as the primary regulators of
439 generative AI. A majority, 88% of academic scientists, underscore the pivotal role that
440 universities should assume, distinguishing them from other key players. National professional
441 associations, journal editors, and publishers also receive notable endorsement, with 74%, 65%,
442 and 61% support respectively, highlighting the broader academic community's involvement in
443 regulation. In contrast, when it comes to entities outside the academic sphere, over half of all
444 academic scientists believe that both the Federal Government (56%) and supranational
445 organizations (54%) should play substantial roles. This distribution of responsibilities suggests
446 a preference for an academic-led approach to generative AI regulation, complemented by
447 governmental and international oversight, to effectively address the intricacies of generative
448 AI's integration into academic settings. Building on this preference for an academia-centered
449 regulatory approach, there is also strong support among academic scientists for federal
450 involvement in the oversight of generative AI's use, with 71% expressing strong or somewhat
451 strong approval. Alongside the preference for an academia-centered regulatory approach, 71%
452 of academic scientists express strong or somewhat strong approval for federal involvement in
453 generative AI oversight.

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To assess how variations in question wording might influence academic scientists' attitudes toward government regulation of generative AI, respondents were randomly assigned to one of four experimental versions of a key survey question: (1) "Which of the following is closest to your current point of view about the role of the government in regulating generative AI?" with responses: "Federal government should not regulate generative AI technology, leaving its regulation to private industry", or "Federal government should ban generative AI deployment until comprehensive research on its potential consequences is conducted"; (2) identical wording but including a moderate response option: "Federal government should regulate generative AI technology, however, it should momentarily step back from doing so until comprehensive research on its potential consequences is conducted"; (3) explicit ethical framing: "Considering the possible ethical and unintended consequences generative AI may have, which of the following is closest to your current point of view about the role of the government in regulating generative AI?" with the same two responses as version 1; and (4) identical ethical framing as version 3, plus the moderate response option included in version 2.

479 **Fig 5. Methodological experiment results: (a) Current opinion about the role of the**
 480 **government in regulating generative AI; (b) Current opinion about the role of the**
 481 **government in regulating generative AI, considering the possible ethical and unintended**
 482 **consequences it may have.** Confidence intervals and sample sizes for each subsample are as
 483 follows: (a1) n = 77, CI = ±11.1%; (a2) n = 50, CI = ±13.8%; and (b1 and b2) n = 52, CI =
 484 ±13.6%.

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486

487 The survey went a step further to dissect academic scientists' attitudes towards
 488 government regulation of generative AI through an experimental approach (Fig 5). This
 489 segment aimed to evaluate how the phrasing of questions, particularly those mentioning the
 490 ethical and unintended consequences of generative AI, alongside the option of a neutral
 491 response, would affect their attitudes for federal regulation. Participants were randomly

492 assigned one of four variations of the question, covering aspects such as outright banning versus
493 not banning generative AI technologies and the inclusion or exclusion of a neutral middle
494 response category. This experiment indicates that the question format in which response options
495 were structured significantly influenced participants' responses. Through this detailed
496 exploration, it became apparent that academic scientists' opinions on generative AI governance
497 are complex, with a considerable number supporting some level of federal oversight, yet their
498 preferences are nuanced, often swayed by the contextual presentation of potential generative
499 AI risks and regulatory options.

500

501 Our analysis reveals academic scientists' nuanced preferences regarding government
502 regulation of generative AI technologies (Fig 5). When presented with a middle-ground
503 response option about the extent of governmental oversight, a clear majority favored this
504 moderate stance (76% and 59% for two different question versions), demonstrating a shift away
505 from more polarized positions. Specifically, the inclination to outright ban generative AI
506 dropped dramatically (from 50% to 8% and 55% to 28% across the two versions) when this
507 middle option was available. Similarly, the preference for no regulation also decreased (from
508 44% to 14% and 38% to 9%), indicating a general consensus towards a balanced regulatory
509 approach. Moreover, when questions explicitly highlighted the potential threats posed by
510 generative AI, there was a noticeable increase in support for temporary bans by the Federal
511 Government until thorough research is completed, with or without a middle response option.
512 This ranged from 50% to 55% without a middle option and jumped from 8% to 28% with it.
513 Additionally, the absence of a moderate option slightly increased the likelihood of respondents
514 choosing not to answer (from 2% to 6%, and from 4% to 7% in the respective question
515 versions). These findings underscore the complexity of academic scientists' attitudes towards

516 generative AI regulation, leaning towards a preference for moderate, well-considered policy
517 approaches that balance potential risks and benefits while awaiting further research.

518

519 **Discussion**

520 The emergence of ChatGPT stimulates new discussion on the adoption of AI-assisted
521 technology in different sectors. This paper contributes to the understanding of university
522 academic scientists' perceptions of the use and regulation of generative AI, as well as their
523 experience using it in teaching and research activities. Drawing from a nationally representative
524 survey of 232 respondents from STEM disciplines, the study reveals that 65% of academic
525 scientists have incorporated generative AI into teaching or research, with 20% actively using it
526 in both fields. Generative AI is predominantly used in educational settings for developing
527 pedagogical materials (51%) and in research primarily for writing, reviewing, and editing tasks
528 (40%). Despite widespread adoption, concerns persist, particularly about misinformation,
529 identified by 78% of respondents as their primary apprehension. The study further indicates a
530 cautious yet optimistic approach among scientists, with 97% of teaching users and 84% of
531 research users intending to continue its use, demonstrating substantial confidence in its potential
532 benefits. Moreover, regulatory attitudes reveal a pronounced preference (88%) for academic-
533 led oversight of AI integration, reflecting skepticism about exclusively governmental
534 regulation.

535

536 This survey's findings align closely with previous research on artificial intelligence in
537 educational and research contexts. Earlier studies already recognized AI's potential in
538 streamlining administrative tasks, facilitating adaptive learning methods, and enhancing
539 personalized education—factors consistently noted even prior to the widespread availability of

540 generative AI [30]. Similar to results presented here, earlier research has highlighted AI's
541 beneficial role in automating text-based academic tasks such as content generation and
542 manuscript preparation, underlining substantial perceived utility among academics [32,79].
543 Additionally, respondents' concerns regarding misinformation and the fabrication of credible
544 yet inaccurate bibliographic citations confirm issues previously documented in empirical
545 assessments of generative AI tools, where substantive citation errors and misinformation have
546 presented persistent challenges [53,54]. Moreover, consistent with previous survey-based
547 studies, academic scientists demonstrate cautious optimism toward generative AI, balancing
548 enthusiasm for potential efficiency improvements against the risks identified related to
549 academic integrity and ethical standards in scholarly publishing [54]. This continuity with
550 established scholarship reflects that the perceptions documented among STEM academic
551 scientists reflect broader, ongoing dialogues around ethical and practical risks inherent to AI
552 integration.

553
554 Notably, this survey also reveals important divergences from prior studies, particularly
555 those involving student populations. Previous literature indicated predominantly positive
556 student attitudes towards generative AI, emphasizing its capacity to improve academic
557 engagement and personalized learning [29]. In contrast, academic scientists surveyed here
558 report comparatively lower rates of generative AI use in activities involving direct interpersonal
559 interaction or subjective evaluation, such as mentoring (17%), grading (11%), or conducting
560 examinations (8%), indicating a selective rather than comprehensive adoption pattern. This
561 divergence suggests a critical distinction between student enthusiasm—driven by immediate
562 educational benefits—and the more cautious, responsibility-driven attitudes of academic
563 scientists, who must balance innovation with preserving academic rigor and ethical standards.
564 Furthermore, unlike earlier optimistic predictions regarding widespread chatbot adoption,

565 which emphasized educational benefits such as personalized learning experiences, skill
566 development, and substantial pedagogical support for educators [80,81], this survey indicates
567 more selective adoption among academics, concentrated predominantly on content creation,
568 and scholarly communication tasks rather than comprehensive integration across all academic
569 functions.

570

571 While the study emphasizes misinformation concerns, other ethical implications warrant
572 deeper exploration. The inherent bias in generative AI models, stemming from biased training
573 data, significantly influences academic use by potentially perpetuating discriminatory
574 outcomes, thus affecting fairness and equality within educational contexts [40]. Data privacy
575 concerns also merit critical attention, especially regarding generative AI's role in processing
576 and sharing sensitive academic and research data. For instance, AI-driven qualitative analysis
577 methods raise important questions about ethical standards for data management [60].
578 Additionally, generative AI poses significant challenges for plagiarism detection, as it can
579 produce highly sophisticated academic content that is nearly indistinguishable from human
580 writing [82]. This limits the effectiveness of traditional detection tools and highlights the need
581 for more advanced identification methods or a reevaluation of current academic integrity
582 standards.

583

584 Regarding generative AI regulation, the study identifies a complex regulatory landscape
585 perceived by academic scientists, who strongly favor (88) an academia-centered regulatory
586 approach, primarily led by academic institutions, with complementary oversight by national
587 professional associations (74%), journal editors (65%), and publishers (61%). Although a
588 majority (71%) of respondents support some federal involvement, their preferences clearly
589 emphasize cautious, evidence-based policies rather than outright governmental bans.

590 Experimental survey data explicitly indicate that academic scientists' regulatory positions vary
591 depending on how AI-related risks are presented, reflecting context-dependent rather than
592 absolute regulatory stances. Current regulatory practices already align with these academic
593 preferences. Universities are actively developing internal AI governance frameworks [55],
594 academic publishers have begun establishing clear editorial standards for AI-generated content
595 [83], and international organizations such as UNESCO have advanced global governance
596 principles to shape national AI policies [84].

597

598 While this study provides valuable insights into the adoption intentions of academic
599 scientists regarding generative AI, several limitations must be acknowledged. First, although
600 based on probability sampling, the findings reflect responses from academic scientists across
601 the six STEM disciplines included in the study, which may not represent the broader academic
602 community. Additionally, as with any cross-sectional study, the findings reflect the period of
603 data collection (late 2022–early 2023), capturing attitudes and experiences during the early
604 adoption phase; perspectives may have since evolved. Nevertheless, the findings of the paper
605 on early-stage adoption behavior and perceptions provide a substantive and valuable basis for
606 informing next stage research design and data collection. Smaller percentage differences should
607 be understood within the survey's overall margin of error ($\pm 6.4\%$), though this does not affect
608 the general interpretation of results, which point to trends in academic scientists' attitudes and
609 experiences. Although no significant differences were observed in responses by gender or
610 academic rank, the final sample does show variation in disciplinary representation. Civil and
611 environmental engineering was more represented, while biology and public health were less so.
612 These differences may reflect varying levels of exposure or familiarity with generative AI
613 across disciplines.

614

615 Furthermore, although the survey did not inquire about other demographic characteristics,
616 it did ask about gender, allowing us to examine data by gender. This is a notable limitation
617 given that generative AI adoption and its impacts might vary across different demographic
618 groups. The lack of race and ethnicity data is significant, especially considering how certain
619 groups have faced disproportionate challenges within academia [85–88]. Additionally, while
620 the survey examined generative AI’s impact on the work of academic scientists, it did not
621 address experiences with generative AI hallucinations or the generation of inaccurate
622 information, which is an emerging concern. Indeed, clear evidence of misuse and malpractice
623 already exists. Generative AI has generated high-quality fraudulent papers that are difficult to
624 detect [82], and it can produce factually incorrect responses, including fabricated bibliographic
625 citations [53,89]. These limitations suggest that future research should explore generative AI’s
626 effects across a wider range of academic disciplines and demographic groups, and more
627 thoroughly investigate issues of accuracy and the reliability of AI-generated content. Such
628 research is crucial for developing a comprehensive understanding of generative AI’s role in
629 academia and ensuring its responsible integration.

630

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894 **S1 Appendix. Non-response bias analysis**

895 We evaluated potential nonresponse bias in our survey sample with two sets of analyses.
896 These examined whether our respondent sample was significantly different across three
897 demographic characteristics (i.e., gender, academic field, and rank) from (a) the initial sample
898 frame used for recruiting SciOPS panel members, and (b) the sample of SciOPS panel members
899 randomly selected as the sample for this survey.

900

901 Table S1 shows the first set of results, which examines demographic differences between
902 survey respondents (n=232) and the initial sample frame of academic scientists in all six fields
903 originally employed to recruit the SciOPS panel (n=18,504). T-test results indicated no
904 differences between survey respondents and the initial sample frame in terms of gender
905 representation. There were also no observed differences by academic rank. Academic scientists
906 in two academic fields were significantly underrepresented in the final sample of survey
907 respondents, compared with the academic field composition of the initial sample used for
908 SciOPS panel recruitment. These included biologists (33.7% of initial sample frame for SciOPS
909 panel recruitment vs. 25.4% of survey respondents, p-value < 0.005) and public health academic
910 scientists (18.4% of initial sample frame for SciOPS panel recruitment vs. 8.6% of survey
911 respondents, p-value < 0.005). Civil and environmental engineers were significantly
912 overrepresented in the final sample of survey respondents (14.5% of the initial sample frame
913 for SciOPS panel recruitment vs. 22.0% of survey respondents, p-value < 0.01).

914

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918 **Table S1.** T-test results for comparison of demographic composition of survey respondents and
 919 initial SciOPS panel recruitment frame.

Construct	Variable	Initial Panel Recruitment sample (%)	Survey Respondents (%)	Group Differences (%)	P-value	
Gender	Female	32.8	35.3	2.5	0.419	
Field	Biology	33.7	25.4	8.3***	0.004	
	Chemistry	13.1	15.9	0.24	0.235	
	Computer and Information Science Engineering	15.6	13.8	1.8	0.435	
	Civil and Environmental Engineering	14.5	22.0	7.5**	0.006	
	Geography	4.7	14.2	9.5***	0.000	
	Public Health	18.4	8.6	9.8***	0.000	
	Rank	Full Professor	41.4	40.1	1.3	0.683
		Associate Professor	20.8	19.0	1.8	0.486
Assistant Professor		20.7	21.6	0.9	0.747	
Non-tenure Track Researcher		17.1	19.4	3.8	0.389	
(n)	(18504)	(232)				

920 * P < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.005

921

922 Table S2 shows the results of an additional set of t-test analyses which compared the
 923 demographic composition of those SciOPS panel members invited to participate in this survey
 924 (n=777) and those academic scientists who agreed to participate (n=232). There were no
 925 significant demographic differences by gender, academic field, or academic rank between these
 926 two groups.

927 **Table S2.** T-test results for comparison of demographic composition of survey respondents and
 928 sample of SciOPS participants.

Construct	Variable	SciOPS Panel Members (%)	Survey Respondents (%)	Group Differences (%)	P-value
Gender	Female	35.6	35.3	0.3	0.940
Field	Biology	23.3	25.4	2.1	0.510
	Chemistry	16.9	15.9	1.0	0.741
	Computer and Information Science	12.0	13.8	1.8	0.475
	Engineering Civil and Environmental	26.5	22.0	4.5	0.152
	Engineering				
	Geography	13.1	14.2	1.1	0.673
	Public Health	8.2	8.6	0.4	0.855
Rank	Full Professor	40.1	40.1	0	0.985
	Associate Professor	19.0	19.0	0	0.978
	Assistant Professor	21.8	21.6	0.2	0.949
	Non-tenure Track Researcher	19.0	19.4	0.4	0.906
(n)		(777)	(232)		

929 * P < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.005

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936 **S2 Appendix. Number of randomly selected institutions for**
937 **sampling scientists**

938

939 **Table S3.** Number of randomly selected institutions for sampling scientists

940

Fields	Number of randomly selected R1 institutions	Number of all R1 institutions
Biology	106	131
Civil and environmental engineering	46	131
Geography	46	131
Public health	61	61
Computer and information science engineering	45	131
Chemistry	62	131

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953 **S3 Appendix. Survey instrument: Generative AI uses and**
954 **impacts in academic research and education**

955
956 **Landing page**

957 **Welcome to SciOPS (Scientist Opinion Panel Survey)**

958
959 Thank you for being a member of SciOPS, a nationally representative panel of the Science,
960 Technology and Innovation (STI) community.

961
962 We are interested in your personal views regarding **the use of generative artificial**
963 **intelligence (AI) in academic research and education**. Thank you for your willingness to
964 participate.

965
966
967 **Consent page**

968 **Welcome to SciOPS (Scientist Opinion Panel Survey)**

969 Thank you for being a member of SciOPS, a nationally representative panel of the Science,
970 Technology and Innovation (STI) community. We are interested in your thoughts
971 regarding generative artificial intelligence (AI) uses and impacts in academic research and
972 education. Thank you for your willingness to participate.

973
974 All information collected is confidential and for comparative purposes only. Any data
975 collected will only be reported as de-identified and shared in aggregate form with
976 other researchers. This survey should take about 10 minutes to complete. By clicking “Start
977 survey” you are providing consent to participate in this survey.

978
979 Participants must be 18 and older. If there is anything about the study or your participation
980 that is unclear or that you do not understand, or if you have questions, you may contact Dr.
981 Eric Welch, EricWelch@asu.edu.

982
983 If you have any questions about your rights as a subject/participant in this research, you
984 may email research.integrity@asu.edu or contact the Chair of the Human Subjects
985 Institutional Review Board, through the ASU Office of Research Integrity and Assurance, at
986 (480) 965-6788.

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Survey instrument

Section 1: Looking Ahead

We would like to begin by asking about your general opinions on some of the changes occurring in the world and how you believe they will impact our lives.

1000 *[s1_q1]* Thinking about the next few years, how much do you think each of the following will
1001 change the way we live in the United States? [The order of items *[s1_q1_a]* to *[s1_q1_g]* is
1002 randomized]

1003 (1 Not at all, 2 Not very much, 3 Somewhat, 4 A lot)

1004 *[s1_q1_a]* The spread of infectious diseases

1005 *[s1_q1_b]* Artificial intelligence

1006 *[s1_q1_c]* Climate change

1007 *[s1_q1_d]* Political polarization

1008 *[s1_q1_e]* Fusion energy

1009 *[s1_q1_f]* Global conflicts

1010 *[s1_q1_g]* Resource scarcity

1011 *[s1_q1_h]* Other (please specify): *[s1_q1_other]*

1012

Section 2: Your perspectives on Generative AI generally

1014

Now we would like to ask you more specifically about your perspectives on generative artificial intelligence (AI) and its potential impact on society.

1017

We refer to generative AI as a system that, in response to prompts written in natural language, dynamically generates content that is, or appears to be, novel.

1020

[Section2_Q2] Does the increased use of generative AI in daily life make you feel _____?

1022 1 More excited than concerned

1023 2 Equally excited and concerned

1024 3 More concerned than excited

1025

[Section2_Q3] How concerned are you about the following potential threats that may be posed by artificial intelligence? [Items order is randomized]

1028 (1 Not at all concerned, 2 Not very concerned, 3 Somewhat concerned, 4 Very concerned, 5

1029 Extremely concerned)

1030 *[Section2_Q3_a]* Misinformation

1031 *[Section2_Q3_b]* Over-reliance on it

1032 *[Section2_Q3_c]* Loss of jobs

1033 *[Section2_Q3_d]* Loss of creativity

1034 *[Section2_Q3_e]* Threat to cyber security
1035 *[Section2_Q3_f]* Loss of privacy
1036
1037 *[Section2_Q4]* Would you favor or oppose having a federal agency regulate the use
1038 of generative AI similar to how the FDA (Food and Drug Administration) regulates the
1039 approval of drugs and medical devices?
1040 (1 Strongly support, 2 Somewhat support, 3 Neither support nor oppose, 4 Somewhat oppose,
1041 5 Strongly oppose)
1042
1043 *Randomization:* Respondents are randomized for different treatment groups for the following
1044 set of questions *[Section2_Q5]*.
1045 If *[randomsetupsection2q5]=1* then show *[Section2_Q5_NoTreatment]* but skip
1046 *[Section2_Q5_TreatmentOnlyOption]*, *[Section2_Q5_TreatmentOnlyQuestion]*, and
1047 *[Section2_Q5_TreatmentBoth]*.
1048 If *[randomsetupsection2q5]=2*, then show *[Section2_Q5_TreatmentOnlyOption]* but
1049 skip *[Section2_Q5_NoTreatment]*, *[Section2_Q5_TreatmentOnlyQuestion]*, and
1050 *[Section2_Q5_TreatmentBoth]*.
1051 If *[randomsetupsection2q5]=3*, then show *[Section2_Q5_TreatmentOnlyQuestion]*,
1052 but skip *[Section2_Q5_NoTreatment]*, *[Section2_Q5_TreatmentOnlyOption]*, and
1053 *[Section2_Q5_TreatmentBoth]*.
1054 If *[randomsetupsection2q5]=4*, then show *[Section2_Q5_TreatmentBoth]*, but skip
1055 *[Section2_Q5_NoTreatment]*, *[Section2_Q5_TreatmentOnlyOption]*, and
1056 *[Section2_Q5_TreatmentOnlyQuestion]*.
1057
1058 *[Section2_Q5_NoTreatment]* Which of the following is closest to your current point of view
1059 about the role of the government in regulating generative AI?
1060 1 Federal government should not regulate generative AI technology, leaving its regulation to
1061 private industry.
1062 2 Federal government should ban generative AI deployment until comprehensive research on
1063 its potential consequences is conducted.
1064
1065 *[Section2_Q5_TreatmentOnlyOption]* Which of the following is closest to your current point
1066 of view about the role of the government in regulating generative AI?
1067 1 Federal government should not regulate generative AI technology, leaving its regulation to
1068 private industry.
1069 2 Federal government should regulate generative AI technology, however, it should
1070 momentarily step back from doing so until comprehensive research on its potential
1071 consequences is conducted.
1072 3 Federal government should ban generative AI deployment until comprehensive research on
1073 its potential consequences is conducted.
1074

1075 *[Section2_Q5_TreatmentOnlyQuestion]* Considering the possible ethical and unintended
1076 consequences generative AI may have, which of the following is closest to your current point
1077 of view about the role of the government in regulating generative AI?

1078 1 Federal government should not regulate generative AI technology, leaving its regulation to
1079 private industry.

1080 2 Federal government should ban generative AI deployment until comprehensive research on
1081 its potential consequences is conducted.

1082

1083 *[Section2_Q5_TreatmentBoth]* Considering the possible ethical and unintended consequences
1084 generative AI may have, which of the following is closest to your current point of view about
1085 the role of the government in regulating generative AI?

1086 1 Federal government should not regulate generative AI technology, leaving its regulation to
1087 private industry.

1088 2 Federal government should regulate generative AI technology, however, it should
1089 momentarily step back from doing so until comprehensive research on its potential
1090 consequences is conducted.

1091 3 Federal government should ban generative AI deployment until comprehensive research on
1092 its potential consequences is conducted.

1093

1094 *[Section2_Q6]* How much do you support or oppose using generative AI for each of the
1095 following purposes? [Items order is randomized]

1096 (1 Strongly support, 2 Somewhat support, 3 Somewhat oppose, 4 Strongly oppose)

1097 *[Section2_Q6_a]* The production of news articles for mass media

1098 *[Section2_Q6_b]* The production of scientific research manuscripts

1099 *[Section2_Q6_c]* The analysis of large data sets

1100 *[Section2_Q6_d]* The provision of public services (e.g., policing, theft-prevention, weather
1101 forecasting, public transit, etc.)

1102 *[Section2_Q6_e]* The improvement of quality control in manufacturing processes or
1103 laboratory experiments

1104 *[Section2_Q6_f]* The production of creative works (e.g., art, music, poetry, etc.)

1105 *[Section2_Q6_g]* The provision of mental health therapy, in place of individual counseling

1106 *[Section2_Q6_h]* The provision of personalized medical care for individuals (e.g., amount of
1107 pain medications to prescribe, screening of medical images, etc.)

1108

1109 **Section 3: Your Academic Experiences with Generative AI**

1110

1111 This section aims to gain insights into the professional views and attitudes of academic
1112 scientists toward AI use in academia.

1113

1114 **Please answer to the best of your knowledge and consider your academic experience**
1115 **with generative AI.**

1116

1117 *[Section3_Q7]* Have you personally ever used any generative AI systems (e.g., ChatGPT,
1118 Bard, Stable Diffusion, Midjourney, DALL-E)?

1119 1 Yes

1120 2 No

1121

1122 *Pre-skip logic:* if *[Section3_Q7]* = 2 (No), then skip *[Section3_Q8]*, *[Section3_Q9]*,

1123 *[Section3_Q10_ContinueToUse]*, *[Section3_Q11]*, *[Section3_Q12]*,

1124 *[Section3_Q13_ContinueToUse]*

1125

1126 *[Section3_Q8]* Have you ever used generative AI for any of the following teaching
1127 activities? Please select all that apply.

1128 1 Developing pedagogical materials

1129 2 Integration in exams

1130 3 Class exercise and experiment activity in using generative AI

1131 4 Designing student assignments

1132 5 Grading and evaluating student works

1133 6 Mentoring students (e.g., email communication, recommendation letter, etc.)

1134 7 Other (please specify): *[Section3_Q8_Other]*

1135 8 I have never used generative AI for any teaching activity

1136

1137 *Pre-skip logic:* if *[Section3_Q8]* != 8, then show *[Section3_Q9]*

1138

1139 *[Section3_Q9]* How frequently do you use generative AI in your teaching activities?

1140 1 Never

1141 2 Rarely (less than once a month)

1142 3 Occasionally (1-3 times a month)

1143 4 Regularly (1-3 times a week)

1144 5 Frequently (more than 3 times a week)

1145

1146 *Pre-skip logic:* if *[Section3_Q9]* != 1 (Never), then skip *[Section3_Q10]* but show

1147 *[Section3_Q10_ContinueToUse]*

1148

1149 *[Section3_Q10_ContinueToUse]* Do you plan to continue using generative AI in
1150 your teaching activities in the future?

1151 1 Yes, definitely

1152 2 Probably

1153 3 No, I'm not planning to use it anymore

1154 4 Unsure at the moment

1155

1156 *[Section3_Q10]* Do you plan to use generative AI in your teaching activities in the future?

1157 1 Yes, definitely

1158 2 Probably

1159 3 No, I'm not planning to use it

1160 4 Unsure at the moment
1161
1162 *[Section3_Q15]* Do you include any of the following policies regarding generative AI use in
1163 your course syllabi?
1164 (1 Yes, 2 No)
1165 *[Section3_Q15_a]* Allow use of generative AI with no restrictions.
1166 *[Section3_Q15_b]* Allow use of generative AI, but ask students to engage critically with the
1167 tool.
1168 *[Section3_Q15_c]* Allow use of generative AI, but ask students to cite it when used.
1169 *[Section3_Q15_d]* Allow use of generative AI, but only for specific assignments.
1170 *[Section3_Q15_e]* Prohibit use of generative AI.
1171 *[Section3_Q15_f]* My course(s) does not lend itself to generative AI tools.
1172
1173 *[Section3_Q11]* Have you ever used generative AI for any of the
1174 following research activities? Please select all that apply.
1175 1 Research conceptualization
1176 2 Data curation
1177 3 Data analysis
1178 4 Funding acquisition (e.g., searching for potential funders)
1179 5 Visualization
1180 6 Writing - original draft
1181 7 Writing - review and editing
1182 8 Other (please specify): *[Section3_Q11_Other]*
1183 9 I have never used generative AI for any research activity
1184
1185 *Pre-skip logic: if [Section3_Q11] != 9, then show [Section3_Q12]*
1186
1187 *[Section3_Q12]* How frequently do you use generative AI in your research activities?
1188 1 Never
1189 2 Rarely (less than once a month)
1190 3 Occasionally (1-3 times a month)
1191 4 Regularly (1-3 times a week)
1192 5 Frequently (more than 3 times a week)
1193
1194 *Pre-skip logic: if [Section3_Q12] != 1, then skip [Section3_Q13] but show*
1195 *[Section3_Q13_ContinueToUse]*
1196
1197 *[Section3_Q13_ContinueToUse]* Do you plan to continue using generative AI in
1198 your research activities in the future?
1199 1 Yes, definitely
1200 2 Probably
1201 3 No, I'm not planning to use it
1202 4 Unsure at the moment

1203
1204 *[Section3_Q13]* Do you plan to use generative AI in your research activities in the future?
1205 1 Yes, definitely
1206 2 Probably
1207 3 No, I'm not planning to use it
1208 4 Unsure at the moment
1209
1210 *[Section3_Q16]* How confident are you of your ability to _____? [Items order is
1211 randomized.]
1212 (1 Not confident at all, 2 Not very confident, 3 Somewhat confident, 4 Very confident, 5
1213 Extremely confident)
1214 *[Section3_Q16_a]* Keep up with advances in generative AI technology
1215 *[Section3_Q16_b]* Fully embrace generative AI technology in your teaching activities
1216 *[Section3_Q16_c]* Fully embrace generative AI technology in your research activities
1217 *[Section3_Q16_d]* Monitor the use of generative AI technology by your students
1218 *[Section3_Q16_e]* Monitor the use of generative AI technology when reviewing grant
1219 applications
1220 *[Section3_Q16_f]* Monitor the use of generative AI technology when reading the professional
1221 literature
1222 *[Section3_Q16_g]* Monitor the use of generative AI technology when reviewing student
1223 admission applications
1224
1225 Section 4: University Policies
1226
1227 **Thank you so much for your participation. This last section asks about specific AI**
1228 **policies or guidelines in academia and in your institution.**
1229
1230 *[Section4_Q17]* In your opinion, which of the following, if any, should have primary
1231 responsibility for regulating generative AI in academic settings?
1232 (1 Yes, 2 No)
1233 *[Section4_Q17_a]* National professional associations (e.g., the Association of American
1234 Universities, the American Council on Education, etc.)
1235 *[Section4_Q17_b]* Publishers
1236 *[Section4_Q17_c]* Academic institutions
1237 *[Section4_Q17_d]* The federal government
1238 *[Section4_Q17_e]* Journal editors
1239 *[Section4_Q17_f]* Supranational organizations (e.g., the United Nations, NAFSA: Association
1240 of International Educators, etc.)
1241
1242 *[Section4_Q18]* Are there any steps or guidelines regarding the responsible use of ChatGPT
1243 or similar generative AI language models now in place in your:
1244 (1 Yes, 2 No, 3 Don't know)
1245 *[Section4_Q18_a]* Department?

1246 *[Section4_Q18_b]* College?
1247 *[Section4_Q18_c]* University?
1248
1249 *Pre-skip logic:* if *[Section4_Q18_a]* =1 then show *[Section4_Q19]*, *[Section4_Q20]*,
1250 otherwise, skip *[Section4_Q19]*, *[Section4_Q20]*.
1251
1252 *[Section4_Q19]* How do your department's guidelines restrict faculty or student use of
1253 generative AI in any way (e.g., teaching, class work, or research)?
1254 1 Guidelines place restrictions only on Faculty use of generative AI.
1255 2 Guidelines place restrictions only on Student use of generative AI.
1256 3 Guidelines place restrictions on both Faculty and Student use of generative AI.
1257
1258 *[Section4_Q20]* Please briefly describe the restrictions pertaining specifically to using AI that
1259 your department places on faculty and/or students. [Open-end]
1260
1261 *[Section4_Q21]* Have you received any training or guidance on the ethical considerations
1262 associated with using generative AI in an educational or research context offered by your
1263 university?
1264 1 Yes, I have received training/guidance.
1265 2 No, I have not received training/guidance.
1266 3 Unsure.
1267
1268 Thank you so much for participating in this survey!
1269
1270

1271
1272